

Financial Analysis of a Solar Mini Grid Power Plant Deployment in Kavumu, DRC: A FINPLAN-Based Approach

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Executive Summary

This report assesses a proposed 30 MW solar mini-grid in Kavumu, DRC using the financial model FINPLAN. The goal was to test project least profitability under varying conditions. The base case uses the current SNEL tariff (194.4 CDF/kWh), assumes production of 125 GWh per year, an exchange rate of 2840 CDF per USD, a discount rate of 17% and an interest rate of 5%.

Key results show that high utilization is essential: if output drops below ~80% of capacity, the net present value turns negative. Under base assumptions, the project only becomes profitable at ~80% utilization and above. However, even with moderate tariff adjustments (e.g. 10% price cuts), the project remains viable if demand stays high. Financing conditions matter too: the model indicates viability only if discount rates stay below about 17%; higher financing costs would make the NPV negative.

Crucially, the analysis highlights currency risk. With DRC's double-digit inflation, fixed CDF pricing would increase profitability risks. Our findings show that a small franc devaluation (1%) makes the project financial unviable if the tariff is in CDF. By pricing or indexing the tariff in USD, however, the project's revenue stream becomes stable to local inflation and exchange shift.

In summary, the solar mini-grid can help expand affordable electricity access in the region, but its financial success depends on robust utilization capacity and smart risk management. Allowing USD-indexed tariffs and supporting productive electricity uses are key policy steps to make this renewable energy investment attractive and sustainable.

1. Introduction

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) continues to grapple with deep-rooted challenges in its electricity sector. Despite possessing vast energy potential, particularly over 100 GW of hydroelectric capacity, only a small fraction (around 3.2%) has been developed [1]. Electricity access remains limited, with an electrification rate of just 21.5% and a total installed capacity of 3,646.5 MW, according to World Bank data (Figure 1) [2]. The national utility, SNEL, oversees over 90% of the country's power infrastructure, which is primarily hydro-based (99%). However, due to aging infrastructure and frequent maintenance constraints, only about half of its 2,498 MW capacity is reliably operational [3].

In its electricity sector policy framework, the DRC outlines the following strategic objectives [4]:

1. Increase the national electrification rate to 30% by 2025 to improve access for households and businesses.
2. Restructure SNEL to enhance operational efficiency and service quality.
3. Export surplus electricity to diversify the country's revenue base and strengthen its role in the regional energy market.
4. Promote the adoption of renewable energy sources hydropower, solar, wind, and biomass to ensure a sustainable and climate-friendly energy mix.

Within this policy landscape, Law No. 14/011 of June 17, 2014 marked a significant milestone in the reform of the DRC's electricity sector. This law codified the liberalization of the energy market, encouraging private investment and management. Its core objective is to make the electricity sector a driver of economic growth by expanding access through increased private sector engagement and public-private partnerships (PPPs) [5].

The town of Bukavu is currently experiencing urban saturation, with expansion trending steadily outward. Reliable electricity access is essential to ensure the viability of new urban zones and to attract population and commercial activity [6]. In response to this growing demand, and in alignment with the country's energy liberalization efforts, we propose the development of a 30 MW solar photovoltaic (PV) mini-grid in Kavumu, near Bukavu. This system aims to provide clean, sustainable electricity to the surrounding communities, supporting inclusive growth and infrastructure development.

The project will be implemented through a special company responsible for designing, financing, constructing, owning, and operating the plant over a 25-year lifetime. Electricity will be sold directly to local consumers. This report outlines the project's technical specifications, financial modeling using FINPLAN, sensitivity analysis results, and relevant policy and investment recommendations.

Figure 1: Installed Capacity by Energy Source in the DRC in 2024 [7]

1.1. Purpose

This study will analyze the financial viability of solar mini grid power plant in Kavumu, DR Congo using FINPLAN.

1.2. Specific Objectives:

To investigate the minimum profitability scenario of the power plant by:

1. Analyzing the impact of the Utilization Capacity
2. Evaluating the effect of the Electricity Price
3. Performing a sensitivity analysis on the discount and interest rate
4. Examining the sensitivity analysis on the exchange rate

2. Methodology

2.1 Technical Details

This study evaluates a 30 MW_{AC} solar mini-grid planned for deployment in Kavumu, South Kivu, DRC, with a 25-year operational lifespan. The site benefits from strong solar irradiation, averaging 5–5.5 kWh/m²/day, ideal for photovoltaic generation [8]. The plant will connect to a medium-voltage distribution line, with an estimated annual output of 125 GWh sufficient to power around tens of thousands of households. Energy production is assumed to remain stable throughout the project life. Construction is scheduled over 24 months (2026–2027), with commissioning in 2028. Table 1 summarizes the system’s technical characteristics.

Table 1: Technical Parameters for the Proposed Power Plant

Installed Capacity	30 MW (solar PV farm)
Annual Energy Production	~125 GWh
Project Lifetime	25 years
Construction Period	24 months (2026 – 2028)
First year of operation	2028
Transmission/ distribution line	MV/LV

2.2. Financial Data

This section outlines the financial structure of the proposed solar mini-grid project, covering capital investment, O&M costs, tariff assumptions, inflation, and exchange rate considerations. The analysis spans a 25-year operational period, with decommissioning anticipated in 2053. The base case assumes a tariff aligned with SNEL’s current rate to ensure both viability and affordability.

The total capital investment is projected at USD 60 million and 28,400 million CDF, in foreign and local currency respectively. We assume 60% of the USD investment is financed via export credit with a 15-year terms at a 5% interest rate. USD and CDF components are phased across the two-year construction period: 60 and 40% for USD and 70 and 30% for CDF in years first and second, respectively.

Annual O&M costs are estimated at USD 1 million, approximately 1.5% of capital investment, covering staffing, maintenance, insurance, and general administration. These costs are assumed constant over the plant’s lifetime.

Revenue is based on a fixed electricity tariff of 194.4 CDF/kWh. Inflation is modeled at 2.95% for USD and 16% for CDF, reflecting local economic volatility [9]. A constant exchange rate of 2,840 CDF/USD is used, though regional instability can push rates beyond 3,000 [9]. The Figure 2 illustrates the variation of the exchange rate for the last 18 years.

Table 2: Financial Data for the Proposed Power Plant

Investment	60 million USD and 28400 million CDF
Financing currency	Foreign (USD) Local (CDF)
Financial Assumptions	Inflation was steady at 16% CDF and 2.95 USD Discount rate at 17%
Operation and USD	1 million Annually Maintenance
Taxes	VAT at 16% on 10% of the investment
Exchange rate	2840 CDF → 1\$ (2025)

Figure 2: Exchange Rate Variation in DRC from 2006 to 2024

2.3. Modeling Approach/Tool Implemented

For this project, FINPLAN will be applied to simulate the 125 GWh solar mini-grid’s financial performance over its 25-year lifespan. The model incorporates investment costs, O&M expenses, revenue from electricity sales, inflation, and loan terms. It calculates NPV and IRR to determine viability and examines financial metrics like DSCR and debt-to-equity to assess project stability and risk. The Figure 3 below shows of the primary input and out form FINPLAN.

Figure 3: FINPLAN Inputs and Outputs

2.4. Scenarios or Sensitivity Analysis

This financial analysis seeks to evaluate how sensitive the key financial indicators Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and shareholders dividend are to changes in selected variables. To determine the minimum profitability case, the analysis will focus on variations across four critical parameters:

- 1) Reduction on the power plant utilization capacity;

To determine the minimum Power Plant Utilization Capacity needed to make the project viable (sensitivity: 0% to 50% with 10% increment) Base case at 125GWh/Y.
- 2) Reduction in electricity prices;

Assess the lowest Cost of Electricity that enables the project to generate profit (sensitivity: 0% to 14% with 1% increment) Base case at 194.4 CDF per kWh.
- 3) Change in interest and discount rate:

Establish the optimum Investment strategy (sensitivity interest rate: 2% to 8% and sensitivity discount rate: 14% to 20%) Base case at 5% for the interest rate and 17% for the discount rate.
- 4) Change in interest and discount rate:

Evaluate long term stability of the project with a resilient tariffication structure (sensitivity: 1% to 5% with 1% increment): Base case at 2840 CDF per 1USD.

3. Results

3.1. Variation of Energy Produced

In this first scenario, the utilization capacity of the Solar Power Plant was assessed at six levels with the aim of evaluating its impact the profitability mainly the NPV, IRR and the dividends. As seen the Figure 4 below, the utilization capacity below 80% (100 GWh), led to a negative NPV but the IRR is decreasing and became zero from 60% Utilization capacity and below.

Figure 4: Impact of Utilization Capacity on NVP and IRR

Figure 5 below shows that a shareholder will only be able to receive a dividend after 7 years of operation periods considering the base case. However, for the lowest profitable utilization capacity shareholders will have to wait for 11 years of operation to receive the first dividend will be even longer. From 60% Utilization capacity the below, the shareholders will receive on dividend throughout the project lifetime.

Figure 5: influence of Utilization Capacity on Dividends

3.2. Variation of Electricity Price.

The base value of the price of electricity is fixed at 194.4 CDF per kWh. This value corresponds to the current electricity price of the SNEL. Considering the minimum profitable utilization capacity (100 GWh per year), as shown in the Figure 6 below, a maximum reduction of 10% from the base case makes the power plant to generate profit. This corresponds to an NPV of 3513.34 million CDF with an IRR of 17.27% for a cost of electricity of 174.96 CDF per kWh.

Figure 6: Impact of Electricity Price on the NPV and IRR

The variation of the cost of electricity slightly affects the year of first dividend being paid to the shareholder. As seen the Figure 7, shareholder will only be able to receive a dividend from 2043. This means a reduction of 10% of the cost of electricity from the base case will only generate 3 years of delay on the shareholder stating arriving their dividend.

Figure 7: Influence of Electricity Price on Dividends

3.3. Variation of Discount and Interest rate

This last case, we will vary both discount and interest rate and record the behavior of NPV and IRR. By changing the interest rate from 2% to the baseline of 8% and discount rate from 14% to 20%.

Figure 8: Impact Discount and Interest Rate on the NPV

Sensitivity analysis shows that the NPV is maximized with the lowest discount and interest rate but this does not affect the IRR. The power remains profitable with a discount rate lower than 17% (see Figure 8 and Figure 9).

Figure 9: Impact Discount and Interest Rate on the IRR

3.4. Variation of Exchange Rate

From the figure 10 below, we can see that the profitability of the project is really sensitive to any fluctuation on the exchange rate when the tariff is fixed in CDF per kWh. Considering a cost of electricity of 174.96 CDF/kWh under 80% of the power plant utilization capacity a slight increment of 1% of the exchange rate from the base case makes the project financially unviable. On the other hand, let see what happens when the tariff is fixed in USD at 0.061\$ per kWh correspond at 174.96 CDF/kWh indexed to the actual exchange rate. In this case, we can see from the same Figure 10 above that the NPV and IRR remain almost constant with any variation of the exchange rate.

Figure 10: Impact of Exchange Rate on NPV and IRR with USD and CDF Fixed Tariff

4. Discussion

The financial model reveals that demand and pricing are critical determinants of project viability. Our sensitivity analysis shows the mini-grid must operate at high utilization to generate positive returns. For this case, operating below about 80% of capacity (roughly 100 GWh/year) yields a negative net present value (NPV). As utilization falls, the internal rate of return (IRR) steadily declines, dropping to zero at around 60% utilization. In practical terms, the base case (125 GWh/year) only becomes profitable: shareholders begin receiving dividends after 7 years; with lower utilization, this payback is delayed (up to 11 years) or never occurs. Thus, achieving high load factors (for example through supporting productive use of electricity) is vital [10].

Electricity pricing also affects returns. The base-case tariff of 194.4 CDF/kWh (current SNEL rate) was tested by reducing prices up to 10%. Even with a 10% tariff cut (to 174.96 CDF/kWh), the project remains profitable at 80% utilization yielding an NPV of ~3513 million CDF and an IRR of ~17.3%. However, lower prices reduce cashflows and delay investor payback. For instance, a 10% price reduction postpones the first dividend by 3

years (from 2040 to 2043) considering the base case. This indicates some flexibility: moderate tariff reductions can be absorbed if utilization is high, but they come at the cost of slower returns to equity [11].

Financing costs exert a large influence. As expected, higher discount or interest rates shrink NPV. The model shows that both metrics peak when financing costs are lowest, and the project stays profitable only if the discount rate is below 17% (with a modest interest rates). If discount rates climb above this threshold (e.g. due to country risk), the NPV turns negative. In policy terms, this underscores the benefit of concessional financing or credit guarantees to keep capital costs down for mini-grids [12].

Currency and inflation risk are particularly acute in the DRC. With tariff fixed in local francs, even small devaluations devastate the project's finances. For example, at 80% utilization and 174.96 CDF/kWh, a 1% depreciation of the franc (relative to the base year) renders the NPV. By contrast, a dollar-indexed tariff fully insulates revenues: our analysis shows that NPV and IRR remain essentially constant under any exchange-rate changes when priced in. In other words, indexing the power purchase agreement (PPA) to USD effectively stabilize revenue value despite double-digit local inflation. Without such an adjustment, DRC's high inflation and unstable exchange rate would erode cashflows over time and likely doom the project. Thus, currency-hedged or USD-denominated PPAs emerge as a practical way to neutralize inflation and exchange-rate volatility [13], [14].

These findings have clear implications. Investors should insist on high utilization (via anchor loads or industrial offtakes) and on USD-indexed tariffs or hedges to secure returns. Regulators and policymakers can enable this by allowing flexible tariff structures and supporting demand growth. For example, facilitating access to productive-use equipment (e.g. agricultural or industrial machines) can raise utilization and revenue [15].

Limitations and Future Work: This analysis is based on modelled scenarios with assumed parameters. It does not account for operational uncertainties (e.g. panel degradation, maintenance outages) or demand growth beyond the base case. The model assumes static tariffs and capacity, and uses a single set of financial assumptions (loan terms, inflation rates). Future research should validate these results against real project data, and consider additional options like energy mixes [16].

5. Conclusion

This study finds that the Kavumu solar mini-grid can be profitable but only under specific conditions. Namely, the plant must operate near full capacity (at least ~80% utilization) and financing costs must remain moderate. Under these conditions, even a 10% tariff cut (174.96 CDF/kWh) yields a positive NPV (~3.5 billion CDF) and a good IRR (~17%). Crucially, fixing the PPA price in USD (or indexing to USD) protects revenues against DRC's high fluctuation of the exchange rate. Absent such measures, currency devaluation would quickly erode returns.

The project remains viable only when demand is strong and currency risk is managed. We recommend that policymakers keep or encourage USD-denominated tariffs and support demand growth through productive-use programs. Additionally, providing low-cost or hedged financing (to keep discount rates under ~17%) will help attract investors. Under these conditions, the solar mini-grid can contribute significantly to rural electrification in the DRC.

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